

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14846039

11

A PROSPECTIVE STUDY TO DETERMINE THE ROLE OF SUBCUTANEOUS CLOSED VACUUM DRAIN IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING LAPAROTOMY

AUTHORS' NAME:

1. DR. ZEEL BHARATKUMAR PATEL

MBBS

GCS MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH
CENTRE,
AHMEDABAD, GUJARAT

2. DR. NIRAV B. PATEL

ASSISTANT PROFESSOR,

DEPARTMENT OF SURGERY,

GCS MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH
CENTRE,
AHMEDABAD, GUJARAT

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR: DR. ZEEL BHARATKUMAR PATEL

EMAIL ID: patelzeel1698@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

OBJECTIVE: To study the effectiveness of subcutaneous closed vacuum drain in reducing surgical site infection in patients undergoing laparotomy (emergency and elective) with regards to the hospital stay duration, BMI and drain presence, and overall in regards to the complications.

METHODOLOGY: This observational, prospective study was conducted at GCS Medical College & Research Centre in Ahmedabad from October 2022 to October 2024. It included 100 patients undergoing both elective and emergency laparotomies to evaluate the incidence of surgical site infections and related complications.

RESULTS:

The study found several key points:

1. **Hospital Stay Duration:** A statistically significant difference was observed in the duration of hospital stay between patients with and without a drain. Patients with a subcutaneous closed vacuum drain had a significantly shorter hospital stay.
2. **BMI and Drain Presence:** A significant difference was found between BMI and the presence of a drain. The presence of a drain had a particularly positive impact on patients with a higher BMI.
3. **Complications:** There was an association between the absence of a drain and an increased likelihood of complications. Patients who did not have a drain experienced more complications compared to those who had one.

CONCLUSION: The study suggests that the use of a subcutaneous closed vacuum drain in both elective and emergency laparotomies can reduce the incidence of SSIs and related complications, especially in patients with higher BMI.

KEYWORDS:

Subcutaneous Closed Vacuum Drain, Surgical Site Infection, Laprotomy(emergency and elective)

INTRODUCTION

Wound healing is major concern after surgical procedure, because of its association with quality of life and morbidity of patients. Infections that occur in the wound created by an invasive surgical procedure are generally referred to as Surgical Site Infections (SSIs) or Incisional Surgical Site Infection (ISSI). Wound infection continues to be a major problem both in terms of how they affect the outcome of surgical procedure and their impact in the length of hospital stay. Patients requiring Emergency laparotomy procedure have increased risk of surgical site infection and delayed wound healing.

Complications following the closure of abdominal layers after correcting the pathology and peritoneal washings are: surgical site infections, wound dehiscence, burst abdomen, wound seroma and wound hematoma.

Wound dehiscence is difficult to manage as reclosure frequently leads to respiratory compromise and hypoxia. If left open, there is increased risk of nosocomial infection in the wound. There are number of methods have been used to reduce these complications from time to time.

Closed vacuum drains in the subcutaneous plane have decreased chances of infection by removal of serum or debris along with elimination of dead space in the plane.

Hence this study was carried out to evaluate the role of subcutaneous closed vacuum drain in reducing surgical site infection in patients undergoing laparotomy (elective and emergency)

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

Aim: To study the effectiveness of subcutaneous closed vacuum drain in reducing surgical site infection in patients undergoing laparotomy (emergency and elective)

Objective: To evaluate and compare surgical site infection, serous discharge, seroma formation and wound dehiscence in the two groups:

Group 1: subcutaneous closed vacuum drain kept in laparotomy wound.

Group 2: No subcutaneous closed vacuum drain kept in laparotomy wound.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

- **STUDY DESIGN:** Observational, Prospective study
- **STUDY AREA:** GCS Medical College & Research Centre, Ahmedabad
- **STUDY POPULATION:** All patients undergoing laparotomy (elective + emergency)
- **SAMPLE SIZE:** 100
- **STUDY DURATION:** October 2022 to October 2024

PATIENT SELECTION

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. Age group more than 15 years.
2. Male and female
3. Elective and emergency laparotomy (via midline incision)

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. All Immunocompromised patients.
2. Traumatic open wounds on abdomen

3. Patient undergoing for tension suturing.
4. Patient taking long term immunosuppression therapy for any disease
5. Previously operated patients
6. Pregnant and lactating mother
7. Patients with anaemic Hb<10 gms(for elective laparotomy)
8. Patients with hepatic and renal insufficiency (for elective laparotomy)
9. Patient who did not want to participate in study.

DATA COLLECTION:

Data was collected by thorough pre structured questionnaire viz. history taking, clinical examination, investigations, collection of peri operative and postoperative complications, and follow up, after getting informed written consent from the patient.

METHODOLOGY:

Patients who met inclusion and exclusion criteria for the study selected and all patients discussed about the nature of the disease, its treatment and possible complications (post operative wound infection, wound gaping, seroma formation, recurrence etc)

- Written consent for the study and surgery obtained.
- In proforma, thorough history, signs and symptoms were recorded.
- Through clinical examination of physical signs was done.

Distribution of study population

An observational, prospective study in which patients were randomized before surgery into two groups by systemic random sampling.

Group A: 50 patients with subcutaneous closed vacuum drain undergoing laparotomy (elective + emergency)

Group B: 50 patients without subcutaneous closed vacuum drain undergoing laparotomy (elective + emergency)

INVESTIGATION DETAILS:

- Complete Blood Count, Urine routine examination
- Coagulation profile (PT, APTT)
- Renal Function Test (Serum electrolytes, Blood urea Serum creatinine)
- Liver Function Test
- X ray chest PA view, ECG.
- Thyroid profile, Echocardiography, Pulmonary function tests if needed
- Contrast enhanced Computed Tomography (CECT) of abdomen as and when required to rule out other abdominal pathology.

Pre-Anesthetic check-up was performed, and after taking pre-operative fitness, patients were planned for surgery.

Thoracic and cardiac evaluations were done, optimization achieved. Glycemic status of the patient was maintained in normal range.

PREOPERATIVE PREPARATIONS:

1. ELECTIVE LAPAROTOMY:

- Patients and their relatives were briefly explained regarding the interventional procedure, after which informed written consent was obtained.
- Patient was kept NPO 8 hrs before surgery,

- Preparation of abdomen from chest to up to mid-thigh was done with shaving hair 4 hours before surgery.
- Inj. Ceftriaxone 1gm IV given at the time of induction.
- Inj. TT 0.5 cc IM given overnight.

2. EMERGENCY LAPAROTOMY:

Patients who underwent for emergency surgery were assessed for pre-operative hematological and pathological investigations relevant to the clinical diagnosis and were shifted to operation theatre after taking written and informed consent for the surgery and to participate in the study

PROCEDURE:

- ❖ Patients were shifted to the operating room.
- ❖ Supine position given
- ❖ General Anesthesia was given as per the need of the procedure.
- ❖ Surgical site was cleaned with povidone iodine and alcohol.
- ❖ Sterile draping done
- ❖ Abdomen opened by midline incision (upper midline and lower midline incision were used according to patient's pathology) using scalpel.
- ❖ After surgical procedure, thorough peritoneal wash was given.
- ❖ EN-Mass closure of midline incision done in all 100 patients.

GROUP A: (50 patients)

- A subcutaneous closed vacuum drain (closed vacuum drain no 16/14) is brought out via a two separate stab incision approximately 4 cm lateral to the midline bilaterally.
- The holes on the drain are within the subcutaneous layer till the black mark (radio-opaque mark). The vacuum drain is fixed to the skin with silk 1no. suture cutting body. The drain is then connected to the closed vacuum drain apparatus.
- Then subcutaneous layer closure was further done.

SUBCUTANEOUS LAYER CLOSURE: (19)

- Subcutaneous tissue opposed by using polyglactin suture 2-0, Round body, atraumatic needle, interrupted manner.
- Each suture bite was 1 cm apart from each margin.
- Distance between two sutures was 1 cm.

SKIN CLOSURE: (19)

- Skin closure done by nylon 2-0, cutting body, traumatic needle, interrupted vertical mattress technique.
- Each suture bite was 1 cm apart from each margin.
- Distance between two sutures was 1 cm

Group B (50 patients):

The other 50 patients where the subcutaneous vacuum drain was not kept, subcutaneous layer and skin closure was done in above mentioned manner.

POST OPERATIVE PERIOD:

- In postoperative period adequate antibiotic coverage was given usually 3rd generation cephalosporins along with anaerobic coverage for the first 5-7 postoperative days via intravenous route and then for 5-7 days via oral route.

- Dressing was opened on post operative day 3 if no discharge or soiling has occurred.
- If the wound is clean then alternate day dressing performed otherwise as and when necessary.
- Complications such as seroma formation, wound infection, serous discharge, wound dehiscence were recorded and compared in both groups
- The dressing was done with povidone iodine and alcohol under strict aseptic precaution with sterile gauze pieces.
- Closed vacuum drain output is recorded daily and the nature of the output was mentioned.
- The drain was emptied daily and was recharged/closed (under pressure) to maintain the vacuum
- If any collection was present on the surgical site, culture sensitivity was taken and antibiotics were changed according to the sensitivity.
- Diet was resumed depending on the concerned pathology.
- Vacuum drain was removed once the daily drain output was <10ml for 24 hours.
- According to the protocol, drain was kept in the subcutaneous layer minimum for 3 days
- Regular chest physiotherapy with 3 ball spirometry was advised
- Early ambulation of the post operative patients was practiced.
- Skin sutures were removed as per protocol after 14 days of post operative period.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Table 1. Age group wise distribution among study participants

Age group (in years)	Frequency (%)
≤ 20	8(8)
21-30	44(44)
31-40	20(20)
41-50	12(12)
51-60	12(12)
>60	4(4)

Among the study participants, 44% were belonging to 21-30 years of age group followed by 20% cases were from 31-40 years of age group. Only 4 participants were more than 60 years of age group. The mean age of study participants was 34.32 ± 11.5 years.

Table 2. Gender wise distribution of patients

Gender	Frequency (%)
Male	60(60)
Female	40(40)

Out of total, 40% were females and 60% were males, in the study.

Table 3. Chief Complains among patients

Chief Complains	Frequency (%)
Bleeding per rectum	3(3)
Acute Pain in abdomen	29(29)
Abdominal Pain	24(24)
Vomiting	20(20)
Diarrhea	18(18)
Something coming out of rectum	6(6)

Out of total, 24% patients had complaint of Pain in abdomen followed by 20% complained of vomiting and 18% cases complained of Diarrhea. While 3% cases had complained of bleeding per rectum and 6% patients had complained of something coming out of rectum. Total 29% patient had complained of acute abdominal pain.

Table 4. Comparison of Chief Complains among patients

Chief Complains	Drain Present	Drain Absent	p-value
Bleeding per rectum	3	0	0.218
Acute Pain in abdomen	17	15	
Abdominal Pain	10	11	
Vomiting	10	10	
Diarrhea	8	10	
Something coming out of rectum	4	2	

There was no association found between chief complaints of both groups.

Table 5. Addiction History among study participants

Variables		Frequency (%)
Addiction History	Smoking	13(13)
	Chewing tobacco	16(16)
	Alcohol	4(4)
	No	67(67)

Among the patients, 33% cases had presence of addiction history in which majority cases had habit of smoking and chewing tobacco.

Table 6. Comparison Addiction History among study participants

Variables		Drain Present	Drain absent	P-value
Addiction History	Smoking	8	5	0.412
	Chewing tobacco	7	9	
	Alcohol	4	0	
	No	31	36	

There was no association found between addiction history among both groups.

Table 7. Comorbidities among study participants

Comorbidities	Frequency (%)
Diabetes Mellitus	11(11)
Hypertension	10(10)
Asthma	3(3)
COPD	1(1)
None	75(75)

Out of total, 11% patients were of Diabetes Mellitus, 10% cases were suffering from hypertension, 3% cases were asthmatic and only 1% patient were suffering from COPD.

Table 8. Comparison of Comorbidities among study participants

Comorbidities	Drain Present	Drain absent	P-value
Diabetes Mellitus	8	3	0.564
Hypertension	6	4	
Asthma	2	1	
COPD	1	0	
None	33	42	

There was no association found between comorbidities among both groups.

Table 09. Removal of Drain after Surgical procedure (n=50)

Duration of removal of Drain	Frequency (%)
3	20 (40)
5	16(32)
7	14 (28)

In the study among Group A patients, 40% patient's drain was removed on day 3 of surgery, while in 32% cases drain removed on 5th day of surgery. Rest 28% patient's drain was removed on/ after 7 days.

Table 10. Occurrence of Complications among patients

Complications	Frequency (%)
Surgical Site Infection	6(6)
Seroma	8(8)
Serous Discharge	10(10)
Wound Dehiscence	7(7)
None	69(69)

Out of total, 8% cases had developed Seroma and other 10% cases had developed Serous Discharge. Total 6% cases had developed Surgical site infection and 7% cases had developed Wound Dehiscences.

Table 11. Comparison of Hospital Stay among both groups.

	Drain present	Drain absent	p-value
Mean Hospital Stay	7.1 ± 3.46	9.74 ± 5.56	0.0053

There was statically significant difference was found between hospital stay and presence of drain. The presence of drain significantly reduced the duration of the hospital stay.

Table 12. Comparison between days of Drain removal and complications

Complications	Day 3	Day 5	Day 7	p-value
Surgical Site Infection	0	0	2	0.547
Seroma	0	1	2	
Serous Discharge	0	2	2	
Wound Dehiscence	2	0	0	
None	29	8	2	

There was no association found between development of complications and Day of Drain removal.

Table 13. Occurrence of Complications among patients

Complications	Frequency (%)
Surgical Site Infection	6(6)
Seroma	8(8)
Serous Discharge	10(10)
Wound Dehiscence	7(7)
None	69(69)

Out of total, 8% cases had developed Seroma and other 10% cases had developed Serous Discharge. Total 6% cases had developed Surgical site infection and 7% cases had developed Wound Dehiscences.

Table 14. Comparison of Hospital Stay among both groups.

	Drain present	Drain absent	p-value
Mean Hospital Stay	7.1 ± 3.46	9.74 ± 5.56	0.0053

There was statistically significant difference was found between hospital stay and presence of drain.

The presence of drain significantly reduced the duration of the hospital stay.

Table 15. Comparison between days of Drain removal and complications

Complications	Day 3	Day 5	Day 7	p-value
Surgical Site Infection	0	0	2	0.547
Seroma	0	1	2	
Serous Discharge	0	2	2	
Wound Dehiscence	2	0	0	
None	29	8	2	

There was no association found between development of complications and Day of Drain removal.

Table 16. Comparison of BMI among Patients (Group A vs Group B)

BMI	Drain Present	Drain absent	P-value
< 25 kg/m²	48	28	0.0405
>25 kg/m²	14	10	

There was an association found between BMI and Presence of Drain.

Table 17. Comparison of Mean BMI in both groups (Group A vs Group B)

BMI	Drain Present	Drain absent	P-value
	22.6 ± 2.11	25.7 ± 3.47	0.041

There was statistically significant difference found between BMI and presence of Drain among patients.

Table 18. Comparison between BMI and Complications (Group A vs Group B)

BMI	Drain	Surgical Site Infection	Seroma	Serous Discharge	Wound Dehiscence	P-value
< 25 kg/m ²	Present	2	2	1	0	0.721
	Absent	3	1	2	2	
>25 kg/m ²	Present	0	1	1	2	0.047
	Absent	1	4	6	3	

In less than 25 kg/m² BMI group, there was no association found in presence of drain and occurrence of complications. In more than 25 kg/m² BMI group, there was an association found in presence of drain and occurrence of complications.

Table 19. Comparison of the presence of Comorbidities and occurrence of Complications

Comorbidities	Surgical Site Infection	Seroma	Serous Discharge	Wound Dehiscence	p-value
Diabetes Mellitus	4	2	1	1	0.0316
Hypertension	0	1	2	1	
Asthma	0	1	2	0	
COPD	0	1	1	0	

There was an association found between presence of Comorbidities and occurrence of complications.

Table 20. Comparison of complications and presence/absence of Drain

Complications	Drain present	Drain Absent	p-value
Surgical Site Infection	2	4	0.402
Seroma	3	5	
Serous Discharge	4	6	
Wound Dehiscence	2	5	
None	39	30	

In absence of Drain group, 4 patients developed Surgical site infection, 5 cases had developed Seroma, 6 cases had developed serous discharge and 5 cases had developed wound dehiscence. There was an association between Absence of drain and complications.

DISCUSSION

- Emergency midline laparotomy (EML) is fundamental to rescue emergency patients who suffer from non-traumatic acute abdomen. [1,2,3].
- Two forms of infections at the surgical site, including incisional surgical site infections (ISSI) and organ/space infections, are encountered in more than one third of patients following EML and also involves those undergoing elective laparotomy. [4]
- ISSI may hinder adjuvant therapy, trigger wound dehiscence, prolong hospital stay and increase re-operations and mortality. [5]
- There is increased risk of ISSI with advanced age, lifestyle (smoking and alcohol intake), medications (steroids and immunosuppressive drugs) and associated comorbidities (diabetes mellitus, hypertension, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, renal insufficiency, etc). [6]
- Prophylaxis against ISSI comprises implementation of updated protocols for operative theatres cleaning, sterilization of surgical instruments and maintenance of sterile barrier around the surgical field. [7]
- Likewise, optimizing patient's specific risk factors, bowel preparation, skin decontamination, prophylactic antibiotics prior to skin incision and maintenance of normoglycemia should be accomplished before surgery. [8]
- Intra-operatively, intra-peritoneal contamination can be diminished by copious washout of the peritoneal cavity and appropriate placement of drains. [9]

Table 21. Comparison of Mean age

	Mean Age
In present study	34.32 years
Harish R et al study [32]	40.94 years
Gilkar A et al, [33]	32.7 years

In the present study, among the study participants, 44% belonged to 21-30 years of age group followed by 20% cases were from 31-40 years of age group. Only 4 participants were more than 60 years of age group. The mean age of study participants was 34.32 ± 11.5 years. While in the study conducted by harish R et al, the mean age was 40.94 years and, in the study, conducted by Gilkar et al, the mean age of study participants was 32.7 years.

Table 22. Comparison of Gender

	Male	Female
In this study	60%	40%
Pandey VK et al, [34]	52%	48%
Kumar S et al[35]	60%	40%

- In the present study, out of total, 40% were Females and 60% were Males. Similar findings were observed in Kumar S et al study. In Pandey V K et al study, 52% were male and 48% were females. There was no statistically significant difference between age and gender of groups A and B.
- In the present study out of the total patients, 24% had complained of Pain in abdomen followed by 20% complained of multiple episodes of vomiting and 18% cases were of severe diarrhea. While 3% cases complained of bleeding per rectum and 6% patients complained of something coming out of rectum. Total 29% patient had complained of acute abdominal pain.
- Among the 100 patients, 33% cases gave addiction history in which majority cases had habit of smoking and chewing tobacco.

Table 23. Comparison of Comorbidities

	Diabetes mellitus	Hypertension
In present study	11%	10%
Pandey VK et al [34]	34%	-
Kumar S et al[35]	12%	-
Ashraf Mohammad El-Badry et al [36]	30%	33%

- Out of total patients, 11% patients were Diabetic, 10% cases were hypertensive, 3% cases were asthmatic and only 1% patient had history of COPD. Similar findings were in study by Kumar S et al study. While In pandey VK et al study 34% cases were Diabetic. In research conducted by Ashraf Mohammad El-Badry et al, 30% cases were Diabetic and 33% cases were Hypertensive.
- In the present study, in Group A (50 patients) 40% patient's removal of drain was done on 3rd day of surgery, while in 32% cases removal of drain on 5th day of surgery. On 7th day 28% patient's drain was removed.

Table 24. Comparison of Mean BMI

	Mean BMI (Drain present)	Mean BMI (Drain absent)
In present study	22.6	25.7
Pandey VK et al [34]	24.07	23.46
Ashraf Mohammad El-Badry et al [36]	29	27

- In the present study, in group A with patients having BMI less than 25 kg/m², there was no association found in keeping the subcutaneous vacuum drain and reduction of complications compared to group B.

- Whereas in group A with patients having BMI more than 25 kg/m², there was a significant reduction in occurrence of complications in comparison to group B, while in study of Pandey VK et al, almost similar BMI and rate of complications was observed in both groups and in Ashraf Mohammad El-Badry et al study, contrast findings than our study was found.
- In the present study in all patients undergoing laparotomy, it was observed that the rate of complications is more in those patients suffering from one or more comorbidities.

Table 25. Occurrence of Complications

Complications	In present study	Pandey VK et al [34]	Kaya E et al [37]
Surgical Site Infection	6%	40%	7.7%
Seroma	8%	40%	15%
Serous Discharge	10%	38%	6%
Wound Dehiscence	7%	28%	12%

In the present study out of the 100 cases, 8% cases developed Seroma and other 10% cases developed Serous Discharge.

Total 6% cases had developed Surgical site infection and 7% cases had developed Wound Dehiscences.

- There was statistically significant reduction in the duration of hospital stay in Group A.
- Among Group A, no association was found between development of complications and Day of Drain removal.
- In Group B, 4 patients developed Surgical site infection, 5 patients developed Seroma, 6 cases had developed serous discharge and case had developed wound dehiscence. There was statistically significant reduction of complications in group A. Similar Findings were seen in Kaya E et al study.

CONCLUSION:

- This prospective study was conducted in Department of General Surgery, GCS Medical College Hospital and Research Centre Ahmedabad, from October 2022 to October 2024. Incidence of surgical site infections including serous discharge, seroma formation wound dehiscence was observed among 100 patients undergoing laparotomy for underline surgical pathology.
- Most of the organisms causing SSI were gram positive cocci which are inoculated during the incision.
- Patients operated in emergency were at a higher risk of developing SSIs due to the late presentation causing widespread peritonitis and unavailability of enough time for adequate antibiotic prophylaxis and pre operative conditioning of the patient. Diabetes Mellitus was the major contributor of SSIs followed by hypertension, Tobacco chewers and Smokers were at higher risk of developing SSI.
- The 50 patients where a subcutaneous closed vacuum drain was kept showed better results in reducing the above-mentioned complications particularly in patients having BMI>25kg/metre square.

- There was reduction in the duration of hospital stay in patients where drain was kept.
- There was no significant change in outcome in patients with BMI<25 by placing a drain in subcutaneous layer.

Hence, on basis of this study we would like to conclude that subcutaneous closed vacuum drain when kept during elective/emergency laparotomy procedures reduce the chances of SSI and related complications

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Mc Geehan G, Edelduok I, Bucholc M et al. (2021): Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Wound Bundles in Emergency Midline Laparotomy Identifies That It Is Time for Improvement. *Life (Basel)*, 11: 138-42.
2. Nally D, Sorensen J, Kavanagh D (2020): Emergency laparotomy research methodology: A systematic review. *Surgeon*, 18: 80–90.
3. Nally D, Sørensen J, Valentelyte G et al. (2019): Volume and in-hospital mortality after emergency abdominal surgery: a national population-based study. *BMJ Open*, 9: 32183-86.
4. Alkaaki A, Al-Radi O, Khoja A et al. (2019): Surgical site infection following abdominal surgery: a prospective cohort study. *Can J Surg.*, 62: 111–117.
5. Watanabe J, Ota M, Kawamoto M et al. (2017): A randomized controlled trial of subcutaneous closed-suction Blake drains for the prevention of incisional surgical site infection after colorectal surgery. *Int J Colorectal Dis.*, 32: 391–398.
6. Mueck K, Kao L (2017): Patients at High-Risk for Surgical Site Infection. *Surg Infect (Larchmt)*, 18: 440– 446.
7. Weiser T, Forrester J, Forrester J (2019): Tactics to Prevent Intra-Abdominal Infections in General Surgery. *Surg Infect (Larchmt)*, 20: 139–145.
8. Ohge H, Mayumi T, Haji S et al. (2021): The Japan Society for Surgical Infection: guidelines for the prevention, detection, and management of gastroenterological surgical site infection, 2018. *Surg Today*, 51: 1–31.
9. Norman G, Goh E, Dumville J et al. (2020): Negative pressure wound therapy for surgical wounds healing by primary closure. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32356396>.

Declaration of patient consent

The authors certify that they have obtained all consent of patient and the patient was assured that his/her images or name would not be published in study and due efforts will be made to conceal the identity.

Financial support and sponsorship

Nil

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.